

Hungarian Teachers' Opinions on Ideal Teacher Interaction

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Abstract

Based on Leary's interpersonal model (Interpersonal Circumplex), Wubbels elaborated the scheme of interpersonal behaviour that was completed by questionnaires (Questionnaire on Teacher Interaction (QTI)). Our research involved 237 teachers. In our survey, we searched for the answer to the question of what opinions teachers held about the ideal interpersonal behaviour. According to the teachers, the main characteristics of the ideal interpersonal behaviour are directive, decisive, helpful, and understanding; it is less characterised by doubt and dissatisfied. Opinions differ on strictness and leniency.

Keywords: *teacher interaction, interpersonal behaviour, QTI query, teachers' opinions.*

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Introduction

The interaction between individuals is considered essential in terms of interpersonal relationships by psychology, communication theory, and sociology alike. According to Buda (1986), the process of education can be interpreted as a chain of interactions between individuals, which can occur at the teacher-student and student-student levels. Based on Watzlawick's communication theory (1967) and Leary's interpersonal behavior model (1957, 2004), Weubbels et al. (1987) developed their own model, as well as a corresponding measurement tool (QTI) allowing the measurement and description of teacher interaction behavior. The Hungarian version of the QTI (Questionnaire on Teacher Interaction) consisting of 48 items was prepared by Horváth-Tóth (2019). The aim of our research is to map the opinions of 237 Hungarian educators participating in the study on ideal teacher interaction and detect differences according to the background variables using the 48-item Hungarian questionnaire.

Theoretical Background

Since the 2000s, there has been increasing focus on developing and implementing tools that allow students to evaluate their teachers (Goh-Fraser 1998; Koul-Fisher 2005; Wubbels et al. 2006; Passini et al. 2015). Classroom interaction can be understood as two-way interpersonal communication, which triggers cognitive and/or emotional

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effects and influences the behavior and actions of the parties involved (Amidon-Hough 1967; Dunkin-Biddle 1974; Mehan 1979). Regarding classroom communication, three main approaches can be distinguished (Tóth-Horváth 2022).

The first is the behaviorist theory, which aims to categorize speech events and determine their frequency. This is evident in the coding of social interaction functions and the analysis of classroom interactions (Erickson 2006; Flanders 1977).

The second approach is the intuitive and qualitative perspective, which relies on sociological and ethnographic research methods. The sociological perspective examines specific speech-behavior patterns and has found that teacher-student interactions, as well as the teacher's relationship with the class, are essential for fulfilling an optimal teaching role (Jordan-Henderson 1995; Erickson 2006). In contrast, ethnographic research applies a quantitative analysis of classroom conversations (Greeno 2006; Jordan-Henderson 1995), emphasizing the primacy of learning as a social system (Erickson 2006).

The third approach is based on personality theories, where the focus of observation extends beyond a specific lesson to encompass behavioral manifestations, personality traits, and characteristics that express a teacher's generalizable interaction in pedagogical situations.

Among these theories, the model of teacher interpersonal behavior developed by Wubbels et al. (1985) stands out. This model, known as the Interpersonal Behavior in Teaching (IPC-T) model, was created by adapting Leary's circumplex model (1957) to the educational context (Leary-Harvey 1956; Tóth-Horváth 2022). Leary's social-interpersonal personality theory is based on Karen Horney's and Harry Stack Sullivan's interpersonal theories. Leary synthesized a system from Horney's and Sullivan's theories and developed a research procedure for it. The Leary personality model depicts 16 interpersonal behavioral variables along two dimensions in a circular continuum, where each type of behavior is interpreted within 8 categories (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Leary's Personality Model Consists of 16 Interpersonal Behavioral Variables

Source: Tóth-Horváth 2022: 60

The vertical axis is determined by the A – I, while the horizontal axis is determined by the E – M behavioural variables. The Leary interpersonal circumplex model consists of 8 categories resp. 8 octants. These are the following: AP: managerial – autocratic, BC: competitive – narcissistic, DE: aggressive - sadistic, FG: rebellious – distrustful (suspicious), HI: self-effacing - masochistic, JK: docile – dependent, LM: cooperative – over-conventional, NO: responsible - hypernormal. Leary assigned diagnostic procedures for this theory, allowing scores to be assigned to each octant, taking into account the intensity indicators (Leary 1957). By adapting Leary's circumplex model (IPC, Leary 1957) to the educational context and incorporating the systems-oriented communication model proposed by Watzlawick (1967), the Model for Interactional Teacher Behavior (MITB) was developed (Wubbels et al. 1985).

Wubbels et al. (1987) applied the general model of interpersonal communication, which Leary (1957) also used as the starting point of his work, allowing the description the teachers' activities based on their students' perceptions (Tóth–Horváth 2022). Wubbels et al. (1987) also provided the 8 personality variables of interpersonal behavior, summarized by Tóth–Horváth in Table 1.

Table 1. Interpretation of the Model for Interpersonal Teacher Behaviour

Name of the variable	Detailed description
DC/ leadership	notice what is happening; lead, organize, give orders; set tasks, propose solutions, explain, arouse the students' interest
CD/ helping ,friendly	assist, show interest in students' problem, involved, behave friendly and politely, sense of humor
CS/ understanding, consensus-oriented	listen with interest, empathic behavior, show confidence and understanding, initiate conflict resolution, patient, open
SC /student responsibility, freedom	provide opportunity for independent work; wait for class to let off steam; give freedom and responsibility; take into consideration the proposals of the students
SO/ uncertain, indecisive	no intervention to happening, stay in background, apologize, wait and see how the wind blow, admit one is in the wrong
OS / dissatisfied, doubtful	wait for silence, consider pros and cons, keep quiet, express dissatisfaction, eyes are angry, always ask questions, criticize
OD/ admonishing	get angry, short-tempered, forbid, warn for mistakes, punish
DO/ strict	control of students, strict exams, strict evaluation, get class silent, maintain silence, set rules and norms, exercise rules

Source: Tóth & Horváth, 2022, 76, (translation provided by LDSz)

The process of teaching and learning is an interactional chain involving the participants, most of which occurs between the teacher and the students, although the issue of interaction among the students themselves cannot be neglected. Tóth–Horváth (2019) already surveyed the opinions of teacher trainees in the Carpathian Basin about the ideal teacher interaction. According to Nikitscher (2015), teachers are increasingly dependent on "market" conditions and the expectations of various school stakeholders, including not only students and the school operator but also the parents.

Research Goals, Questions, and the Research Sample

The presented research aims to map and characterize the ideal teacher interaction from the perspective of educators, and then compare the results with the opinions of teacher trainees in the Carpathian Basin. To achieve this, we used the Hungarian translation of the 48-item QTI survey introduced by Fisher et al. (1995) translated by (Tóth–Horváth

2022). The original survey uses a 0...4 scale, which was converted to a 1...5 scale. We worked with the 1...5 scale. The research was conducted online in Hungary. The data was processed using the SPSS statistical program. A total of 237 educators participated in the study. The research addressed to answers the following questions:

- (Q1) What is the opinion of educators on ideal teacher interaction?
- (Q2) Is there a significant difference among the QTI variables concerning the five background variables examined (gender, age, type of residence, type of institution where the educator teaches, type of subject taught)?

The demographic data of the teachers were as follows:

- gender: male – 34,6% (82 participants); female – 65,4% (155 participants)
- age: 23-30 – 8,9% (21 participants); 31-40 – 39,7% (94 participants); 41-50 – 18,1% (43 participants); 51-60 – 29,5% (70 participants); above 61 – 3,8% (9 participants)
- type of residence: capital – 7,6% (18 participants); town – 70,9% (168 participants); village – 16,9% (40 participants); farm/rural area – 4,6% (11 participants)
- type of institution, where the teacher is employed: elementary education (elementary school) – 42,2% (100 participants); secondary education (secondary vocational school, secondary grammar school) – 24,9% (59 participants); tertiary education (college, university) – 32,9% (78 participants)
- type of the subject taught: Humanities (literature, history, languages, etc.) – 38% (90 participants); Sciences (Mathematics, Informatics, etc.) – 53,2% (126 participants); Economic subjects – 8,9% (21 participants)

The data of the participating educators were examined according to several criteria. The distribution based on the gender and age of the educators is presented in Table 2. In the study, a total of 82 male and 155 female educators participated. Majority of the respondents (94 individuals) fall into the age category between 31 and 40. The fewest respondents (9 individuals) were aged 61 or above.

Table 2. Gender and Age Distribution of Educators

		Gender		Total
		male	female	
Age	23-30	3	18	21
	31-40	34	60	94
	41-50	14	29	43
	51-60	31	39	70
	61 and above	0	9	9
Total		82	155	237

Source: own editing

Table 3 presents the distribution of educators who completed the questionnaire based on the types of subjects they teach. In the case of Humanities, the number of respondents is the same for both genders. In the case of Science subjects, 19.8% (25 individuals) of the respondents were male and 80.2% (101 individuals) were female. For Economic subjects, 57% (12 individuals) of the respondents were male and 43% (9 individuals) were female.

Table 3. Distribution of Educators Based on Gender and the Type of Subject Taught

		Gender		Total
		male	female	
Type of subject	Humanities	45	45	90
	Sciences	25	101	126
	Economic subjects	12	9	21
Total		82	155	237

Source: own editing

Table 4 presents the distribution of educators who filled out the questionnaire based on the type of educational institution where they teach. 42% of the respondents teach in primary education institutions (elementary school), 25% teach in various secondary education institutions (vocational school, secondary grammar school), while 33% teach in tertiary education institutions (college, university).

Table 4. Distribution of Educators Based on Gender and the Types of Educational Institutions

		Gender		Total
		male	female	
Type of institution	Elementary school	23	77	100
	Secondary school	19	40	59
	Tertiary education	40	38	78
Total		82	155	237

Source: own editing

Results

This chapter of the study present descriptive statistical indicators of the QTI variables obtained from the 237 educators and illustrate their relationship structure. The questionnaire consisted of 48 items, each containing six elements belonging to one of the eight octants of interpersonal teacher behavior, mixed within the questionnaire. The respondents were unaware of which elements corresponded to which octants of interpersonal teacher behavior. When completing the questionnaire, educators could indicate their responses using a Likert scale. The Likert scale is a measurement scale used to assess attitudes, ranging between two extreme values. The smallest value on the Likert scale was 1, indicating that the given attribute is not part of the ideal interpersonal behavior, while the highest value was 5, indicating a strong attribute. The Cronbach alpha coefficient was computed for each QTI scale as a measure of internal consistency. Table 5 reports the reliability of each of the eight scales of the QTI (N=237).

Table 5. Reliability Indices of the Wubbels' QTI Measurement Tool in the Presented Research

Acronym (EN)	Categories of teacher interpersonal behavior according to Wubbels	Cronbach-alfa
ADM	Admonishing	0,885
DIS	Dissatisfied	0,770

HFr	Helping/friendly	0,768
LEA	Leadership / decisive	0,776
SRE	Student freedom	0,870
STR	Strict	0,889
UNC	Uncertain	0,799
UND	Understanding, consensus seeking	0,700

Source: own editing

The data in Table 5 suggest that the QTI has satisfactory reliability, with scale coefficients ranging from 0.70 to 0.89 with the whole sample. Table 6 reports the reliability of each of the eight scales of the QTI for gender (male=82, female=155) and the type of institution the education process takes place.

Table 6. The Reliability of Each of the Eight Scales of the QTI for Gender and the Type of Educational Institution

Acronym (EN)	Cronbach-alfa				
	Male	Female	Elementary education	Secondary education	Tertiary education
ADM	0,872	0,892	0,889	0,881	0,884
DIS	0,771	0,768	0,775	0,746	0,777
HFr	0,697	0,794	0,831	0,770	0,652
LEA	0,845	0,627	0,811	0,821	0,622
SRE	0,883	0,868	0,874	0,859	0,872
STR	0,853	0,904	0,887	0,887	0,891
UNC	0,800	0,798	0,800	0,800	0,796
UND	0,754	0,668	0,735	0,610	0,710

Source: own editing

Table 7 presents the descriptive statistics indicators of the entire sample according to the types of teacher interpersonal behavior. None of the teacher interpersonal behavior categories in the examined sample follow a normal distribution.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics for the 8 Octants

	ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Mean (M)	8,66	8,14	27,70	28,09	17,28	14,90	7,18	26,49
Standard deviation (SD)	3,274	2,110	2,967	2,010	4,769	5,338	2,380	2,793
95% Confidence Interval Lower Bound	8,24	7,87	27,32	27,83	16,67	14,22	6,87	26,14
95% Confidence Interval Upper Bound	9,08	8,41	28,07	28,35	17,89	15,59	7,48	26,55
Normal distribution	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Source: own editing

Figure 2 presents the averages of the octants in the circumplex diagram. Based on these, it can be concluded that according to the opinions of the surveyed teachers, ideal teacher interactions are characterized by high values of assertive, decisive, helpful, friendly, and understanding attitudes, while low values are associated with admonishing, warning, uncertain, indecisive, dissatisfied and skeptical attitudes. There

is a divergent opinion regarding ideal teacher interaction in the strict-assertive (STR) and student freedom (SRE) dimensions.

Figure 2. QTI Variables in the Circumplex Diagram
Source: own editing

The QTI variables were also examined with respect to the following background variables: *gender, age, type of residence, type of educational institution where the teacher teaches, and type of subject taught*. In Table 8 (Appendix), we provided the means (M) and standard deviations (SD) for the sub-samples according to these background variables.

We examined whether there are significant differences among the samples along the various background variables. Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used for comparing the means. Table 9 presents the results of the Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests (Asymp. Sig.).

Table 9. Results of the Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis Tests in Terms of Octants

Background variable	ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Gender (Mann-Whitney U. Asymp. Sig.)	0,543	0,041	0,725	0,003	0,164	0,186	0,452	0,368
Age (Kruskal-Wallis H. Asymp. Sig.)	0,597	0,851	0,7694	0,981	0,919	0,468	0,196	0,729
Type of residence (Kruskal-Wallis H. Asymp. Sig.)	0,779	0,785	0,172	0,044	0,247	0,953	0,897	0,237
Type of institution (Kruskal-Wallis H. Asymp. Sig.)	0,421	0,311	<0,001	0,646	0,450	0,183	0,154	0,726
Type of subject (Kruskal-Wallis H. Asymp. Sig.)	0,169	0,208	0,009	0,972	0,850	0,272	0,802	0,639

Source: own editing

In terms of gender, significant differences were found regarding the following two octants (Table 9): **DIS** (male teachers perceive the ideal teacher as significantly less dissatisfied and doubtful compared to female teachers); and **LEA** (male teachers perceive the ideal teacher as significantly less directive and assertive compared to female teachers). Regarding the age of teachers, no significant differences were found in the case of any octant.

Concerning the type of residence, a significant difference was found in the **LEA** dimension. According to teachers living in cities/towns, the ideal teacher is perceived as significantly less directive and assertive compared to the teachers residing in smaller settlements. The table with the lowest and highest averages for QTI octants based on the teachers' residence type is summarized in Table 10.

Table 10. The Highest and Lowest Means of QTI Octants in Terms of Residence

	ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Capital	*		*					
Town		*		*		*		
Village	***				*		*	*
Farm/rural residence		***	***	***	***	***	***	***

Note: *: the lowest mean, ***: the highest mean according to the type of residence

Source: own editing

The highest average was obtained in the case of 7 octants among teachers living in settlements smaller than villages. Only in the case of scolding - warning attitude of teachers we received the highest average among teachers living in small settlements. We also examined differences in teacher's place of residence as follows: we grouped teachers living in the capital and in the town into one group, and teachers living in settlements smaller than towns into another group. In Table 11 (appendix), we provided the average (M) and standard deviation (SD) of the samples according to this grouping.

We summarized the lowest and highest averages of QTI octants according to the type of teachers' place of residence in Table 12. The results are presented based on new classification: Teachers living in the capital or town formed one group, a further group was formed by those teachers who live in smaller settlements than towns.

Table 12. The Highest and Lowest Means of QTI Octants According to Place of Residence of the Respondents

	ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Capital/town	*	*	***	*	*	*	***	*
Smaller than town	***	***	*	***	***	***	*	***

Note: *: the lowest mean, ***: the highest mean based on the place of residence of the teachers participating in the survey

Source: own editing

Regarding the type of institutions where the teachers work, we also conducted a correlation analysis. Since the octants are not normally distributed, we applied Spearman's correlation (Table 13).

Table 13. Results of Spearman's Correlation in the Case of QTI Octants

	ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Spearman correlation (Correlation Coefficient)	0,084	0,011	-0,032	0,055	-0,028	-0,013	-0,056	-0,006

Source: own editing

In the examined sample, we did not find any correlation between the types of institutions where the teachers work and the eight octants examined. Regarding the types of subjects taught by the teachers, we also conducted correlation analysis. Since the octants are not normally distributed, we used Spearman's correlation in this case as well (Table 14).

Table 14. Results of Spearman's Correlation in the Case of QTI Octants

	ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Spearman correlation (Correlation Coefficient)	0,100	0,005	-0,194	0,012	-0,036	0,002	-0,019	-0,060

Source: own editing

In the examined sample, we did not find any correlation between the types of subjects taught and the examined 8 octants. Regarding the types of subjects taught, we examined the means of sub-samples. The results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Comparison of Means of Sub-Samples in the Case of Subjects Taught by the Teachers

Source: own editing

Regarding the types of subjects taught by the teachers, we found a significant difference only in the case of **HFR** octant among the 8 octants: Kruskal-Wallis $H = 0.025$ (Figure 3). Teachers who teach subjects related to Science and Economics, perceive the ideal teacher to be much less characterized by helpfulness and friendliness compared to teachers who teach Humanities.

In Table 15, we examined whether there is any correlation between the different octants. Since the octants are not normally distributed, we used Spearman correlation here as well.

Table 15. Scale Intercorrelations for QTI

QTI Scale	Scale Intercorrelation							
	ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Admonishing	---	0,486	-0,508	0,165	-0,363	0,488	0,289	-0,461
Dissatisfied		---	-0,169	0,007	0,029	0,848	0,298	-0,028
Helping/Friendly			---	-0,111	0,695	-0,163	-0,013	0,737
Leadership				---	0,181	-0,130	0,066	0,069
Student Resp./ Freedom					---	0,070	0,304	0,951
Strcit						---	0,705	-0,060
Uncertain							---	0,065
Understanding								---

Source: own editing

The categories of Student responsibility and Understanding (0,951), Helping/friendly and Understanding (0,880) correlate highest and positively. The categories of Admonishing and Helping/friendly correlates highest and negatively (-0,543). Figure 4 illustrates the characteristic assumptions of the model of interpersonal teacher behaviour using the Understanding scale's correlations with its adjacent and opposite scales.

Figure 4. Profile of Scale Intercorrelations for Understanding Scale

Source: based on Fraser, Aldridge, Soerjaningsih (2010, 28) own editing

Answers Provided for Research Questions

The present study targeted to answer two research questions. The first research question (Q1) was the following: *What is the opinion of educators on ideal teacher interaction?* In Figure 2, we illustrated the averages of responses provided by teachers in terms of eight octants. According to the respondents, the ideal teacher interactions are characterized by high values of directive, decisive, helpful, friendly, and understanding, consensus-seeking attitudes, while low values characterize scolding, warning, uncertain, indecisive, dissatisfied, and skeptical attitudes. Regarding the dimensions of strictness (STR) and student responsibility (SRE) categories, the opinion of respondents on ideal teacher interaction are divided. It is not a coincidence that these two dimensions show the highest values for standard deviation (SRE: 4.769; STR: 5.338). In Figure 5, we present the distribution of responses for the strictness (STR) octant. It can be seen that the distribution of responses is quite wide. 11.8% of the respondents (28 teachers) gave the fewest possible points for this octant (6x1 point), one teacher gave 22 points, while 19.4% (46 teachers) gave 21 points for this octant out of a maximum of 30 points (6x5 points).

Figure 5. Distribution of Responses Obtained for Strict (STR) Octant
Source: own editing

The second research question (Q2) was formulated as the following: *Is there a significant difference among the QTI variables concerning the five background variables examined (gender, age, type of residence, type of institution where the educator teaches, type of subject taught)?* Table 9 presents the results of the Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests, which reveal significant differences according to background variables. Regarding gender, significant differences were found in the **DIS** and **LEA** octants. Male educators perceive the ideal teacher to be significantly less dissatisfied and doubtful than female educators do. Additionally, male educators perceive the ideal teacher to be significantly less directive and assertive than female educators do. No significant differences were found concerning the age of the educators. Concerning the type of residence, significant differences were observed in the **LEA** dimension. Educators residing in urban areas perceive the ideal teacher less directive and assertive compared to those residing in smaller communities. Regarding the type of institution where educators

teach, significant differences were found in the **HFR** (helpful - friendly) octant. Teachers at tertiary institutions (colleges, universities) perceive the ideal teacher less characterized by a helpful and friendly attitude compared to those teaching at secondary educational institutions (secondary vocational schools, secondary grammar schools). Significant differences were also found based on the type of subject taught, specifically in the **HFR** (helpful - friendly) octant. Teachers of Sciences and Economics subjects perceive the ideal teacher less characterized by helpful and friendly attitude compared to those teaching Humanities.

Conclusion

In our presented study, we reported the results of research conducted among educators (237 participants). 82 male and 155 female teachers participated in the research. We obtained answers to two research questions formulated at the beginning of our research. We obtained information how educators perceive ideal teacher interpersonal behavior. We intend to compare these findings with those of a study conducted by Tóth & Horváth (2019), which surveyed the opinions of educators in the Carpathian Basin on the same topic. Their study involved 336 participants (J. Selye University: Komárno, Slovakia: 146 participants; II. Rákóczi Ferenc Carpathian Hungarian College: Beregszász, Ukraine: 45 participants; Partium Christian University: Oradea, Romania: 128 participants; University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Hungarian Language Teacher Training: Subotica, Serbia: 17 participants). We compared the results obtained by Tóth & Horváth with the results of the present study. In Figure 6, we depicted the averages of the octants of the two studies in a circumplex diagram.

Figure 6. Comparison of Presented Research with the Research Results of Tóth-Horváth (2019)

Source: own editing

The highest discrepancy between the averages of the two surveys was observed in the case of **HFR** and **STR** octants. According to educators' perceptions, the ideal teacher interpersonal behavior is much less characterized by strictness and assertiveness, as well as by helpfulness and friendliness, compared to the opinions of teacher candidates in the Carpathian Basin.

The smallest difference between the averages of the two surveys was found related to **UND** and **SRE** octants. The opinion of teachers and teacher trainees in the Carpathian Basin mostly aligns regarding the understanding-consensus-seeking and lenient - soft-hearted attitudes. The average of the octants based on the two surveys is presented in Table 16.

Table 16. Comparison of the Averages of the Present Study and the Research Conducted by Tóth & Horváth (2019)

	ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Averages of the survey conducted among educators	1,44	1,36	3,96	4,68	2,88	2,48	1,20	4,42
Averages of the survey conducted among teacher trainees in the Carpathian Basin (Tóth & Horváth 2021)	1,59	1,62	4,46	4,50	2,77	2,76	1,36	4,45
Deviance	-0,15	-0,26	-0,50	0,18	0,11	-0,28	-0,16	-0,03

Source: own editing based on Tóth & Horváth (2022, 80)

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Appendix

Table 8. Means and Standard Deviations of the QTI Octants According to Background Variables

Background variables		ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Gender	Male M	8,4390	7,7073	27,878	27,4268	16,8780	14,2195	7,0244	26,1341
	Male SD	3,1431	1,9531	2,6359	2,6714	4,5390	4,8611	2,2715	3,0541
	Female M	8,7806	8,3742	27,6000	28,4387	17,5032	15,2645	7,2581	26,6839
	Female SD	3,3445	2,1597	3,1326	1,4419	4,8862	5,5550	2,4384	2,6353
Age	23-30 M	7,6190	7,6667	27,6190	28,1277	18,2381	13,0952	6,2857	27,1429
	23-30 SD	2,5392	2,1056	3,1540	1,9134	5,5489	5,4581	1,3093	2,9544
	31-40 M	8,6170	8,2447	27,3830	28,1277	17,0106	15,2340	7,1489	26,4255
	31-40 SD	3,2598	2,1083	3,4613	1,9135	4,5425	5,0957	2,3735	2,7297
	41-50 M	9,0698	8,3488	27,9302	27,8605	17,3256	15,2326	7,8140	26,2791
	41-50 SD	3,4114	2,1809	2,1974	2,6239	5,0082	5,8872	2,7882	2,8479
	51-60 M	8,7143	8,0714	28,1429	28,1286	17,3571	14,7571	7,1143	26,5143
	51-60 SD	3,3499	2,0874	2,3547	1,8172	4,7519	5,2542	2,3501	2,8220
	above 61 M	9,2222	7,7778	26,5556	28,2222	17,2222	15,2222	7,0000	26,5556
	above 61 SD	4,8006	2,2236	4,2164	1,3017	4,9188	5,7831	2,1213	3,0046
Type of residence	Capital M	8,3889	8,2778	27,1667	28,0556	17,7778	15,3333	7,3333	26,9444
	Capital SD	2,8726	2,1090	3,8079	1,9844	4,6723	5,3358	2,5668	2,6451
	Town M	8,5893	8,0476	27,5060	28,0357	17,1429	14,8214	7,1607	26,3929
	Town SD	3,2266	2,0816	2,8725	1,9296	4,6716	5,2132	2,3658	2,8538

	Village M	9,1250	8,3500	27,2750	28,4750	17,0000	14,9250	7,0500	26,2750
	Village SD	3,6528	2,2481	2,8192	1,8945	5,1141	5,7037	2,3089	2,7734
	Farm/rural settlement M	8,5455	8,6364	28,6364	29,0000	19,7273	15,3636	7,6364	28,0909
	Farm/rural settlement SD	3,4457	2,2033	1,3618	0,7746	5,0416	6,5310	2,8026	1,6404
Type of institution	Elementary school M	8,3100	8,0300	27,4000	27,8600	17,3200	14,6400	7,2000	26,4300
	Elementary school SD	3,0705	2,0863	3,3151	2,3399	4,8135	5,3438	2,4121	2,8964
	Secondary school M	8,6949	8,5085	28,0339	28,1695	17,7288	15,8983	7,6271	26,8305
	Secondary school SD	3,2708	2,0709	1,9997	1,9312	4,4984	5,2578	2,6903	2,4716
	Tertiary education M	9,0897	8,0128	27,2051	28,5256	16,9103	14,4872	6,8077	26,3205
	Tertiary education SD	3,5095	2,1652	2,8529	0,9633	4,9364	5,3640	2,0326	2,8987
Type of subject	Humanities M	8,3556	8,0333	28,3778	27,6778	17,5333	14,6000	7,2000	26,6667
	Humanities SD	3,1205	2,0850	1,5330	2,7553	4,8695	5,4066	2,4135	2,8835
	Sciences M	8,6905	8,3254	26,9524	28,4444	17,1270	15,3730	7,2143	26,4365
	Sciences SD	3,3406	2,1385	3,4196	0,9762	4,6562	5,2820	2,4054	2,6638
	Economic subjects M	9,8095	7,5238	26,9524	28,4762	17,1905	13,3810	6,8571	26,0952
	Economic subjects SD	3,4003	1,9905	3,0574	1,0305	5,1829	5,2486	2,1514	3,2234

Source: own editing

Table 11. Averages and Standard Deviations of QTI Octants According to the Type of Teacher's Place of Residence

Background variables		ADM	DIS	HFR	LEA	SRE	STR	UNC	UND
Place of residence	Capital/town M	8,5699	8,0699	27,7097	27,9570	17,2043	14,8710	7,1774	26,4462
	Capital/townSD	3,1875	2,0796	3,0548	2,0686	4,6628	5,2127	2,3791	2,8322
	Smaller than town M	9,0000	8,4118	27,6471	28,5686	17,5882	15,0196	7,1765	26,6667
	Smaller than town SD	3,5833	2,2197	2,6520	1,7118	5,1737	5,8258	2,4059	2,6658

Source: own editing

